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Master Degree in
Environmental Change and Global Sustainability

**“Study of Spatial Distribution and
Temporal Evolution of Snow Cover and
Snow Depth, using reanalysis data over
Karakoram, Himalaya and Kunlun
Mountains”**

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Dedication

They say humanity only made it this far because of our ability to bond, cooperate, and rely on one another. I am not sure if I can speak in the name of humanity but speaking on my brief experience on Earth so far, nothing was truly done alone in my case. I proudly had incredible support in every part of my story, and naturally this work being a chapter of it, it was not different. I can say that this thesis work only exists thanks to an entire support system of great people that kept me thinking, moving and going on.

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Abstract

The word “Himalaya” means ‘abode of snow’ in Sanskrit, reflecting the central role of snow in the region’s environment and livelihoods. Snow cover and snow depth are essential for regional climate dynamics, impacting billions of people, and influencing water availability, hydropower and climatic balance. Studying spatial distribution and investigating the interannual, annual and seasonal variation in snow across this region is therefore fundamental. If assessed on a long-term basis, it is also useful for monitoring Climate Change and the connected impacts. The most recent Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) report indicates the continuing decline in seasonal snow duration and glacial mass, with reductions in snow covered areas and snow volumes decreasing in most regions of the Himalayas, further supported by recent studies that already identified snow diminishing in recent decades. Therefore, this thesis aims to investigate the temporal evolution and the spatial distribution of snow cover and snow depth in the Kunlun, Himalaya and Karakoram Mountains, latitudes 20°N to 40°N and longitudes 70°E to 100°E, with the reanalysis produced by ECMWF-ERA 5 Land from 1951 to today.

ERA5-Land reanalysis dataset provided by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) offers high resolution climate data with a spatial resolution of 9 km and hourly data resolution. Snow cover and snow depth data were processed using RStudio, ideal to manage and manipulate the extensive dataset. The spatial distribution of snow cover and snow depth was analyzed on annual, seasonal, and monthly basis, and maps were generated for specific sub-periods (e.g., 1991–2023 and 2000–2023). For temporal analysis, trends in snow cover were achieved using linear regression and the Mann-Kendall test to determine their significance and calculated for the mean regional series and for individual grid points to identify regional patterns in snow cover evolution.

The analysis of the annual mean snow cover distribution from 1951 to 2023 shows that 48.6% of (or 51% if we account the sea) of the gridded area can be considered snow free, while 49% is considered snow-covered, meaning it each grid point has from 1% to 100% of snow coverage. Although the snow peaking close or exactly of 100% coverage is more present in the western region, there are more snow-covered grid points in the eastern part of the area, specifically where the Karakoram Mountain range is. Conversely, areas with no snow cover

correspond to the lower areas in altitude, and mainly below latitude 30° N, including most of India, and especially the central part of the country. Snow depth distributions follow a similar spatial pattern, with the deepest snow found in the highest snow-covered areas, those with coverage ranging 90-100%, particularly concentrated in the western regions. In the seasonal analysis, Winter consistently showed the highest snow accumulation, followed by Spring, and Autumn while Summer exhibited minimal snow presence. Autumn, as the snow accumulation season, showed more grid points with at least 1% snow cover compared to the other seasons. Monthly analysis further supported the seasonal trends, with February usually showing the highest snow cover, while April marks the decrease, and August records the least snow. Snow depths show a more consistent pattern, with less variations seasonally, but still, some in lower snow depths, while deeper snow (>1m) remained stable through the year.

Lastly, examining individual years, the year with the highest snow cover was 1957, with an average annual snow cover of 19.9 %, in contrast, the year with the lowest snow cover was 2016, with 13.7% average annual snow cover. The temporal analysis revealed a statistically significant negative trend in snow cover from 1951 to 2023, with a decline of -0.28% per decade. Moreover, the rate of decline has accelerated in the most recent decades (1991–2023), moving to -0.60% per decade, statistically significant as well. However, in the 2000-2023 period, the snow cover trend of -0.49% per decade is no longer statistically significant, with a p-value > 0.05 confirmed with the Mann-Kendall test, likely due to the shorter dataset duration with respect to the high interannual variability observed in the data. For the regional approach towards temporal evolution, statistically significant slopes were filtered in relation to not significant ones, resulting in 23% of the whole area presenting significant change in snow cover between 1951 and 2023. The strongest significant negative trends, for individual grid points, were observed in the eastern region of the study area, while the Karakoram and western Himalayas showed less pronounced negative changes in snow, with some areas even suggesting positive trends, though most of these positive slopes were proven not statistically significant. Given the size of the study area, this work could benefit from a more local separation of regions, and detailed examination of the regional trends in order to understand snow dynamics in the Himalayas.

Table of contents

Chapter 1	9
1.1 Snow formation	9
1.2 Snow Importance	10
1.3 Himalayan Climatic & Hydrological Characteristics	11
1.4 Importance of Snow Studies in the Himalaya Region	13
Chapter 2	16
2.1 Measuring Snow	16
2.1.1 Reanalysis dataset on Snow Cover and Snow Depth	16
2.1.2 ERA5 and ERA5-Land	18
2.2 Remote Sensing & Satellite Products on Snow Studies	20
2.3 Literature Review	21
Chapter 3	25
3.1 Study Area	25
3.2 Data Acquisition	26
3.3 Data Preparation	26
3.3.1 Spatial Distribution Analysis	27
3.3.2 Temporal Evolution and Trends Analysis.....	28
Chapter 4	29
4.1 Results	29
4.1.1 Spatial Distribution	29
4.1.2 Temporal Evolution and Trends	36
4.2 Discussion	40
4.2.1 Representativeness of the Dataset & key findings in comparison with literature	40
4.2.2 Study Limitations.....	42
4.3 Conclusion	43
References	45

Figures and Tables

Figures

Figure 1 Accumulated annual snowfall divided by annual runoff over the global land regions. The value of this dimensionless ratio lies between 0 and 1 and is given by the colored scale, R. The red lines indicate the regions where streamflow is snowmelt-dominated. (Barnett et al., 2005).....	10
Figure 2 Synthesized Map of the Asian Water Tower Area: Hydrological Features and Atmospheric Circulation (Yao et al 2022).....	13
Figure 3 A schematic of the reanalysis process from ECMWF.....	17
Figure 4: Study Area limits and main basins	25
Figure 5 Spatial Distribution of Snow Cover (%) and Snow Depth (m) Across Study Periods (1951–2023, 1991–2023, 2000–2023), latitudes 20°N to 40°N and longitudes 70°E to 100°E. On the left there are Mean Snow Cover Distribution maps for the 3 studied periods, with the scale ranging from 100-0% Snow Cover. On the right, Mean Snow Depth Distribution for the three studied (1951-2023, 1991-2023, 2000-2023) periods with values ranging from 0 to 10 m	31
Figure 6 Seasonal Mean Snow Cover Distribution (%), 1991-2023, latitudes 20°N to 40°N and longitudes 70°E to 100°E. Seasonally Snow Cover Distribution maps for the 1991-2023 studied periods, with the scale ranging from 100-0% Snow Cover: Winter, Spring, Summer and Snow.....	32
Figure 7 Monthly Mean Snow Cover Distribution maps, for the 2000-2023 study period , latitudes 20°N to 40°N and longitudes 70°E to 100°E, with the scale ranging from 100-0% Snow Cover. January, February, March, April, May, June, July, August, September, October, November and December.....	36
Figure 8 Trend in Snow Cover Annual Mean along 1951-2023.....	37
Figure 9 Annual Trend in Snow Cover, 1951-2023, latitudes 20°N to 40°N and longitudes 70°E to 100°E, before the statistical significance test, with scale ranging red (negative slopes from -0.4%/year) to blue (positive slope until 0.2%/year).....	38
Figure 11 Annual Trend in Snow Cover, 1951-2023, latitudes 20°N to 40°N and longitudes 70°E to 100°E, after the statistical significance test, with scale ranging red (negative slopes from -0.4%/year) to blue (positive slope until 0.2%/year).....	40

Tables

Table 1 : ERA5 x ERA5-LAND Comparison based on Copernicus website	20
Table 2 Key Findings of Literature Review.....	24
Table 3 Distribution of Snow Cover (%) and Snow Depth (m) Across Study Periods (1951–2023, 1991–2023, 2000–2023): % total grid points.....	30
Table 4 Seasonal Snow Cover and Snow Depth Distribution, 1991-2023 period	33
Table 5 Monthly Snow Cover and Snow Depth Distribution, 1991-2023 period & 2000-2023 period	34
Table 6 Statistical Trend and Significance of the Trend in Snow Cover Annual Mean 1951-2023	37
Table 7 Statistical Trend and Significance of the Trend in Snow Cover Annual Mean 1991 - 2023 and 2000-2023	38

Table 8 Mean Slope per decade 1951-2023, percentage of positive slope, percentage of negative slope.....39

Table 9 Mean Slope per decade 1951-2023, percentage of positive slope, percentage of negative slope, after statistical test.....40

List of Acronyms

ECMWF European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts

HTESSEL Tiled ECMWF Scheme for Surface Exchanges over Land

MODIS Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer

NDSI Normalized Difference Snow Index

NSIDC National Snow and Ice Data Center

RCM Regional Climate Model

SCF Snow Cover Fraction

SD Snow Depth

SWE Snow Water Equivalent

Chapter 1.

1.1 Snow formation

Precipitation is essentially the fall of water that forms in the atmosphere and reaches the surface of Earth. There are different forms of precipitation based on atmospheric conditions, and the main ones are rain and snow.

The initial phase of snow formation involves the condensation of water vapor into ice, by passing the liquid phase, resulting in snow crystals. This occurs when warm and moist air is lifted and cools at altitude, typically at the interface of differing air masses. As the air rises and cools, water vapor condenses into supercooled droplets which can freeze upon contact with condensation nuclei, dust particles in the providing the surface needed for droplets to freeze and initiate the formation of snow crystals. If temperatures are below -40°C , freeze directly, forming ice crystals that grow into snow crystals. As snowflakes aggregate and fall, they may encounter different atmospheric layers, further altering their shape and size by the time they reach the ground (Libbrecht, K G 2007).

Snow will not fall evenly anywhere, nor will it accumulate evenly, because conditions in the atmosphere and on the ground will vary. Essentially, if the ground temperature is at or below freezing, the snow will reach it. However, the snow can still reach the ground when the ground temperature is above freezing if the conditions are right. In this case, snowflakes will begin to melt as they reach this higher temperature layer, the melting creates evaporative cooling, which cools the air immediately around the snowflake. If able to accumulate snow crystals on the ground, this layer is commonly called snow cover. (Pomeroy, J.W., & E. 2001; National Snow and Ice Data, 2024).

The accumulation and preservation of snow on the ground is influenced by multiple factors, including but not limited to, atmospheric and ground temperature, topography, snowfall frequency, snow density, climatic shifts, atmospheric circulation patterns, and human activities. In general, higher elevations are more likely to receive more snowfall and preserve snow for a longer period. Snow accumulation is inherently seasonal, typically increasing during colder months and melting as temperature increases. Moreover, the shape and features of the land also play a role; surface slope, for instance, receives less or more solar radiation depending on orientation. Steep surfaces can result in snow redistribution such as avalanches or snow slides, further influencing local snow cover stability and runoff patterns (Gurung

et al., 2017; Immerzeel et al., 2009; Shrestha et al., 2015).

1.2 Snow Importance

Water is essential for human sustain, with most of the world's supply sourced from rivers that can rely heavily on seasonal snowmelt. In a snow dominated region, this seasonal snowmelt is very sensitive to changes in precipitation and temperature in fact, Mountainous areas such as the Rocky Mountain Range, The Alps and Himalayas, are also called “the water towers” of the world, as they supply a substantial part of the world freshwater demand (Barnett et al., 2005; Immerzeel et al., 2020).

Snowmelt-dominated regions, generally occupy parts of the globe that are at latitudes greater than 25° N (Figure 1), these regions include northern China, northwestern India, areas south of the Himalaya Hindu Kush, northcentral USA, and some coastal areas of western North America and Europe.

Figure 1 Accumulated annual snowfall divided by annual runoff over the global land regions. The value of this dimensionless ratio lies between 0 and 1 and is given by the colored scale, R . The red lines indicate the regions where streamflow is snowmelt-dominated. (Barnett et al., 2005)

The Himalaya Hindu Kush region is perhaps the most critical region when glaciers and snow cover changes will negatively affect water supply. This region not only is one of the most densely populated on Earth, but also concentrates most of ice mass, after the Arctic and Antarctic regions. For this reason, it is called the Third Pole. In addition, the hydrological cycle here depends on different climatic features, such as the Asian Monsoon and the Westerlies making it highly complex and sensitive to climatic variability (Barnett et al., 2005). Despite this contribution to the world water supply, snow has also a role in regulating global climate through the albedo effect, that reflects most of the incoming solar radiation back to the atmosphere, creating a local cooling effect. As temperature increases, reduced snow cover decreases albedo, increasing solar absorption and accelerating regional warming, enhancing snow and ice melting. (Mukherji et al., 2019; Vavrus, 2007).

1.3 Himalayan Climatic & Hydrological Characteristics

'Himalaya' means 'abode of snow' in Sanskrit, derived from 'hima' (snow) and 'ālaya' (abode), a term by the ancient pilgrims of India who traveled in these mountains. This mountain chain was formed by the collision of the Indian and Eurasian tectonic plates around 50 million years ago, being a geologically young mountain range with more than hundreds of peaks, some of them rising above 8,000 meters, including Mount Everest. Such topography significantly influences regional climate by forming a barrier between the Tibetan Plateau to the north plains of the India to the south, intercepting monsoon winds and generating orographic precipitation (Shrestha et al., 2015; Zurick et al., 2005).

The Himalayas not only form a barrier, but also redirect the south monsoon winds, a seasonal wind shift caused by the different temperature between the Indian ocean and land, causing a release substantial amounts of rain over northern India before reaching the Tibetan Plateau. During this wet period, the western and central areas of India receive more than 90% of their total annual precipitation. The monsoon, along with disturbances from the mid latitude westerlies, winds flowing from the west to east, alter snowfall patterns in the region. The westerlies contribute significantly to winter snowfall across the Karakoram in winter and spring seasons which are responsible for almost 60–70% of snow nourishment in the region annually, while the monsoon provides most of the summer rainfall in on the eastern and southern mountains in the region. With summer rain from the Monsoon and high-altitude snow accumulation from the Westerlies, the Karakoram benefits from both systems (Hewitt et al., 1989;

Ménégoz et al., 2013; Shaw, 2019.;).

The climate in the Karakoram area ranges from semiarid in altitudes lower than 1500 m, to sub-humid with most rainfall in elevations higher than 2500 m, where precipitation reaches 1000 mm annual rainfall. (Khan et al., 2020). At altitudes above 4000 m range from 1000 mm to more than 3000 mm a year. Around 5000 m altitude, approximately 90% of the annual precipitation falls as snow, meanwhile in the lower regions of valleys, snow contributes no more than 10% of the total precipitation (Winiger et al., 2005). In contrast, the Tibetan Plateau and the lower regions north of the Himalayas has precipitation pattern mainly affected by the westerlies. The western part of the Tibet region, is characterized by a drier climate, experiencing an annual average precipitation ranging between 100 and 250 mm. In contrast, the eastern part of Tibet receives more precipitation, with rainfall ranging from 400 to 1000 mm annually (Wang et al., 2018). The dynamics of precipitation will have a big influence on snow and ice, and consequently on water runoff, especially during pre-monsoon and dry seasons, when meltwater is essential. Hydrologically, the region can be divided into endorheic basins (closed lakes and internally in flowing rivers) located mostly in the central and northern parts, and exoreic basins (outflowing rivers) located mainly in the south, as illustrated in Figure 2. The large-scale atmospheric circulation is one of the main drivers of hydrological changes. Atmospheric reanalysis and in situ data demonstrate that seasonal shifts in the Indian monsoon and westerlies are the primary mechanism shaping the spatiotemporal distribution of atmospheric water vapor and precipitation over the region, contributing to around 77% of the region's total precipitation. These circulation processes, combined with climate change, affect also the surface energy budget, which changes temperature and melting patterns (Yao et al., 2022).

Climate change impacts the variability of these hydrological patterns, warming rates in the region are twice the global average, and precipitation regimes have shifted, increasing in the north-west, and decreasing in the south. This not only affects water availability, but also potentially exacerbating extreme weather events like storms and flash floods. In addition, the rate of warming typically increases with altitude, meaning temperature will increase more in high mountains than at low altitudes. (Immerzeel et al., 2009; Yao et al., 2022).

Figure 2 Synthesized Map of the Asian Water Tower Area: Hydrological Features and Atmospheric Circulation (Yao et al 2022)

1.4 Importance of Snow Studies in the Himalaya Region

Snow has a major role in the climate system and its hydrological cycles, especially in regions such as the Karakoram, Western Himalaya, and Kunlun Mountains. For about a quarter of the world's population, seasonal water supply is impacted by the snowmelt and glacier melt from these regions, through the main rivers, such as Indus, Ganges, Brahmaputra and Yellow. (Immerzeel et al., 2010; Shrestha et al., 2015; A. Thapa & Muhammad, 2020). Beyond its utilitarian value, snow is an environment component with sacredness and meaning in local belief, serving not only as a source of recreation, but also as part of their identity and culture, shaping their interactions with the environment and their responses to climatic changes. Climate change can, in fact, endanger the integrity of these services, thus it is critical to monitor changes in snow to protect these resources and the populations that depend on them (Mukherji et al., 2019).

Snow cover can be defined as the layer of snow on the earth's surface that mainly results from snowfalls and has an important impact on the thermal balance and climate

system due to the large difference in albedo between snow covered bare surfaces, with typical albedo values ranging from approximately 0.80–0.95 for fresh snow, 0.70 for average snow, 0.5 to old snow, 0.03–0.10 for the ocean, and 0.05–0.60 for bare ground (Grenfell & Maykut, 1977). Snow depth is the amount of snow that has accumulated on the ground, from the surface to the top. Changes in snow depth can affect seasons timing, in a sense that delayed melting or rapid snow accumulation for example can shift seasonal norms, affecting not just temperature but also the timing and distribution of precipitation (Immerzeel et al., 2009, 2010). Atmospheric temperature itself is the main determinant in the presence or absence of snow on a surface, as many studies had concluded this high correlation between snow measurements and air temperature (Azizi & Asaoka, 2020; Banerjee et al., 2024; Brown, 2000; Gurung et al., 2017).

Indeed, the warming rate of the Tibetan Plateau is twice the global average and ongoing climate warming results in environmental changes that significantly impact the regional to the large-scale hydrological cycle, water resources supply, ecosystem services, and geological hazard risks in High Mountain Asia (Pang et al., 2020; Yao et al., 2019). Global Climate Change is altering snow cover and water resources in the Himalayas. Projected temperatures increase of until 2°C by 2050 for the region, accelerating snowmelt, impacting seasonal water availability, increasing the likelihood of floods and droughts (Shrestha et al., 2015). The Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), monitoring temperature anomaly with reanalysis ERA5, reported that 2024 is the first year to exceed 1.5°C above pre-industrial level. ERA5 is the fifth-generation reanalysis dataset of the European Centre for Medium Range Weather forecast that provides hourly data on atmospheric, land, and oceanic climate variables. The IPCC 2021, the intergovernmental panel on climate change report, future projections indicate continuing decline in seasonal snow duration and glacial mass, with reductions in snow-covered areas and snow volumes will decrease in most regions of the Himalayas. Snowline elevations are expected to rise, and glacier volumes are projected to decline, with greater mass loss under higher CO₂ emissions scenarios, both RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios predict long-term declines in water availability due to reduced snow cover and altered precipitation patterns, posing significant risks to downstream communities. However, in the late century under RCP 4.5, an increase in snow cover is projected during autumn (Azizi & Asaoka, 2020).

Snow studies typically deal with variables such as snow cover area, snow depth, and snow water equivalent. Often utilize remote sensing data from the MODIS (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer) satellite products. Additionally, reanalysis datasets offer data in a broader period, which help in constructing longer term trends. By integrating different approaches, researchers can capture a detailed picture of how

snow has evolved over time under the influence of climatic changes.

The goal of the current thesis work is to investigate the temporal evolution, spatial distribution, variability and trends of snow cover and snow depth in the Kunlun, Himalaya, and Karakoram Mountains. The present research utilizes reanalysis data, specifically the fifth generation of European Reanalysis, the ERA5-Land. The primary objective is to study snow cover and snow depth temporal evolution, considering the whole period of available data (1950 - 2023), and the spatial distribution using the norms calculated over two specific time windows: 1991-2023 and 200-2023. The findings will improve our knowledge of snow cover and snow depth trends in relation to climate change.

Chapter 2.

2.1 Measuring Snow

In the past, snow was manually observed and measured, which provides reliable source of localized data, but might miss regional representation. In the Himalaya most of the existing surface's studies, including snow cover studies, are with remote sensing methods (Vishwakarma et al., 2022). The use of satellite remote sensing for mapping snow cover started around the 1960's, and since the 2000's, satellite observations, such as NASA's Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS).The National Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC), introduced a more precise way to estimate snow cover, yet their short time span limits their applicability for long-term climate analyses (Dietz et al., 2012).

In high-altitude domains like the Karakoram, Himalayas, and Kunlun Mountains significant challenges in snow measurement remain, especially due to its complex environment, the lack of consistent hydro-meteorological datasets and limited in-situ observations. Reanalysis data can bridge this observation and satellite data gap by integrating observations and model outputs to produce datasets with extensive temporal coverage. There are very few attempts at integrating different data types, and combining different datasets in this region(Vishwakarma et al., 2022).

2.1.1 Reanalysis dataset on Snow Cover and Snow Depth

Reanalysis data combine historical observations and ground sensors with numerical weather prediction models to provide spatially and temporally continuous datasets of Earth's climate, being widely used for climate monitoring and studies. They support numerical weather prediction by providing a reference against which the quality of forecasts can be checked. Unlike point-based in situ measurements, which are often costly, and limited to specific locations, reanalysis datasets offer "maps without gaps" covering vast areas and longer periods. ERA5, the reanalysis dataset from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) for example, spans from 1940 to the present. Once completed, an ECMWF reanalysis dataset, embody a record of the global atmosphere, land surface and ocean waves for a given period, and it involves integrating data from the Global Observing System, including satellites, aircraft, ships, and surface observations, with numerical models using data

assimilation techniques. This enables the reconstruction of continuous climate records. As illustrated in Figure 3, the global observing network provides essential inputs, while the Weather Forecast (ECMWF) model assimilates these data to produce long-term climate reanalyses (Hersbach et al., 2020; Slivinski, 2018).

Figure 3 A schematic of the reanalysis process from ECMWF

Many studies have attempted to validate atmospheric reanalysis over the Himalayan region, in special in terms of temperature or precipitation, however, there have been not many studies on snow depth or snow cover with global reanalysis dataset (Orsolini et al., 2019). Snow depth represents the instantaneous grid-box average thickness of snow on the ground and combined with snow density can estimate the snow water equivalent (SWE), which quantifies water stored in the snowpack. Snow depth used to be measured only manually, providing valuable localized data but lacking regional representation, once it cannot be achieved in super high altitudes. Advances in reanalysis data, such as ERA5-Land, now offer modelled snow depth with high spatial resolution enabling more comprehensive assessments of snowpack dynamics over time and space. However, snow depth estimates are subject to biases in precipitation and sublimation processes, requiring careful validation, particularly in remote regions. Snow cover, on the other hand, represents the fraction (%) of a cell or grid-box occupied by snow, and plays role in regulating the Earth's energy balance through its influence on surface albedo. Unlike snow depth, snow cover captures spatial

variability and reflects seasonal and interannual changes in snow distribution. The Himalayan snow cover exhibits significant spatial and temporal variations regulated by seasons, topography, and hydrometeorology (Gurung et al., 2017).

There are many aspects to be considered when selecting the variable studied and the technique to estimate it. Combining snow depth and snow cover analyses offers a more comprehensive understanding of snow behavior, including its distribution, water storage capacity, and response to climatic changes. Moreover, the choice of technique should align with the objectives of the study and the characteristics of the area under investigation. In regions with diverse and complex climatic conditions, such as the Himalayas, Karakoram, and Kunlun Mountains, no single approach is likely to suffice. The majority of studies have chosen to analyse snow cover variability with satellite derived observations, while the extent of regional snow depth variability and its driving mechanisms is less explored (Zhang et al., 2021). This emphasizes the need of integrating in situ observations, satellite data, and reanalysis outputs for a detailed evaluation of snow dynamics in this unique terrain.

2.1.2 ERA5 and ERA5-Land

ERA5, developed by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), is the fifth-generation reanalysis dataset that reconstructs past weather and climate conditions. It employs the Tiled ECMWF Scheme for Surface Exchanges over Land (HTESSEL), a model that simulates extremely detailed water and energy exchanges between the land and the atmosphere. ERA5 provides a horizontal resolution of 31 km and hourly temporal granularity, offering a high level of detail across a wide range of surface and atmospheric variables. At the time of writing, ERA5 spans from 1940 to approximately five days behind real time, assimilating extensive observational data from the upper air and near-surface environments. The ERA5 atmospheric model is coupled with a land surface model and a wave model, ensuring a comprehensive representation of climate processes.

ERA5-Land was created by rerunning the land component of ERA5. The main advantage compared to the prior one, is the higher spatial resolution of 9 km, significantly enhancing its applicability for analyzing land surface processes, including snow cover and snow depth. Moreover, ERA5-Land does not assimilate observation directly, relying instead on atmospheric forcing parameters from ERA5, adjusted with lapse rate corrections to better represent near-surface conditions. It

provides a consistent description of the evolution of water and energy cycles over land from 1950 to five days behind real time.. (Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021).

The primary difference, when it comes of snow variables, between ERA5 and ERA5-Land lies in the treatment of data assimilation. ERA5 assimilates snow depth information from both satellite data and in situ snow depth (SD) for elevations below 1500m, and from that generates snow cover fraction (SCF) data from it. The fact that SD assimilation is limited to elevations below 1500 m, which reduces its effectiveness for high-altitude regions. ERA5-Land, however, offers enhanced snow mass and depth estimates at mid-altitude mountains due to its higher resolution, which provides better orographic contours and temperature adjustments. (Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021). While ERA5 includes variables such as snow albedo, snow density, snow depth, snow evaporation, snow melt and total column snow water, it does not directly measure snow cover. On the other hand, ERA5-Land directly includes snow depth and snow cover. When it comes to limitations, ERA5 discontinuities in data assimilation are more likely introduce artificial trends than ERA5-Land (Hersbach et al., 2020). Moreover, both ERA5 and ERA5-Land are known to overestimate precipitation and snow accumulation, especially in high-altitude regions, that can result in overestimated snow cover and snow depth, as observed in both reanalysis datasets (Li et al., 2022; Orsolini et al., 2019).

Despite these limitations, reanalysis datasets remain indispensable tools for studying snow variability and its response to climate change, offering robust datasets to address gaps in remote and inaccessible regions. A detailed comparison of the two datasets is provided in Table 1, based on information collected from the Copernicus Climate Change website, summarizing their key features, strengths, and limitations of these reanalysis data set.

Table 1 : ERA5 x ERA5-LAND Comparison based on Copernicus website

	ERA5	ERA5-Land
Period	1940 - present	1950 - present
Horizontal Resolution	31 km grid spacing 137 levels, 0.25° x 0.25°	9 km grid spacing, 0.10° x 0.10°
Temporal Resolution	Hourly	Hourly
Data Assimilation	IFS Cycle 41r2	No data assimilation; relies on single model simulation
Strengths	Comprehensive dataset covering atmospheric and surface variables, longer period span	Enhanced spatial resolution; consistent trends due to absence of data assimilation; reduced computing needs, improved hydrological cycle modeling
Limitations	Limited assimilation at high altitudes; larger error spread in complex terrains; overestimate snow accumulation, no direct snow cover output, influenced by model and observations errors	Mixed performance in high altitudes; influenced by model and observations errors; biases in regions with limited observational inputs, overestimate snow accumulation
Example Application	"Global temperature last year"	"Snow Cover in the Himalaia last season"

2.2 Remote Sensing & Satellite Products on Snow Studies

For investigating the snow cover, satellite remote sensing methods have been widely used once it allows detection of spatial temporal patterns across very large areas in inaccessible terrain. The most used on snow studies is the product of moderate resolution imaging spectroradiometer (MODIS), based on the Normalized Difference Snow Index (NDSI), which identifies snow cover by comparing the high reflectance of snow in the visible spectrum to its low reflectance in the shortwave infrared band. The surface covered by snow is very reflective in visible light. However, it doesn't reflect shortwave infrared light well. The MODIS sensors use this difference in reflectiveness between the two types of light to determine where snow is present. Areas that are highly reflective in visible light but not in shortwave infrared light are likely covered in snow. While MODIS has strengths such as global coverage and consistent data availability, it is limited by challenges like meteorological conditions, such as cloud cover, which can obscure snow detection. Algorithms have been developed to mitigate this issue, including merging multiple observations over time to reduce gaps caused by clouds. In general, MODIS based snow cover results have high degree of accuracy, with less than 10% error for the snow presence (Desinayak

et al., 2022; Immerzeel et al., 2009; Salomonson & Appel, 2006)

It is not uncommon to compare satellite products with ground observations to assess the accuracy, once ground observations are measurements taken on the field, not affected by clouds. Nevertheless, meteorological stations will have spatial limitations, more likely limited to lower topography. A comparison of snow cover observations in Tibet showed a good correlation between the methodologies, still it revealed an overestimated snow cover during light snow conditions and underestimated it during heavy snow (Basang et al., 2017).

2.3 Literature Review

Recent research on snow data in the Himalayan region commonly shows a decrease in snow cover area, correlating with both temperature and elevation (Banerjee et al., 2024; Desinayak et al., 2022; Gurung et al., 2017; Thapa et al., 2021). The MODIS snow product, a satellite product, remains the most widely dataset used due to its extensive coverage and high-resolution data. However this dataset is not without limitations, including cloud cover and a relatively short temporal span, as the first year of data availability is 2000 (Banerjee et al., 2024; Desinayak et al., 2022; Dharpure et al., 2021; A. Thapa & Muhammad, 2020; Thapa et al., 2021). On the other hand, reanalysis datasets such as ERA-Interim, ERA5, and ERA5-Land have primarily been utilized to analyse climatic variables like temperature and precipitation, and not so often for snow variables (Dharpure et al., 2021; Dixit et al., 2024). When considering studies related to snow, previous research has largely focused on evaluating the accuracy of snow depth and snow water equivalent (SWE) in reanalysis datasets (Li et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2021). Only a few studies (Li et al., 2022; Orsolini et al., 2019) have systematically assessed the performance of snow depth and snow cover in reanalysis datasets within the Himalayan region. This fact, underscore the need for further investigation into snow-related variables in reanalysis datasets to improve accuracy and enhance their utility in understanding regional snow dynamics.

Research utilizing MODIS satellite data indicates in general, slight decrease, particularly at higher elevations, and identify significant correlations with regional topography and climatic factors like temperature and precipitation. These analyses usually include annual, seasonal and monthly distributions, revealing significant negative correlations between temperature and snow cover, notably in higher elevation zones. Precipitation exhibited positive correlations with snow cover in

specific elevation bands, emphasizing the importance of moisture availability for snow accumulation (Banerjee et al., 2024; Desinayak et al., 2022; Dharpure et al., 2021; Dixit et al., 2024; Gurung et al., 2017; A. Thapa & Muhammad, 2020; S. Thapa et al., 2021). Studies report more significant declines in snow cover in the eastern parts of the Himalayas, being Brahmaputra basin where the most variations were observed (Banerjee et al., 2024; Desinayak et al., 2022; Dharpure et al., 2021; Dixit et al., 2024). For instance, Dharpure et al. (2021) noted that the Eastern Himalayas showed a declining trend in snow cover area, contrasting with the stable or slightly increasing trends in the Karakoram, Western, and Central Himalayas. Longer study periods generally provide a clearer picture of trends, capturing both the annual variability and longer-term changes driven by climatic factors. Climatologists often consider 30 years the ideal period for defining climatic trends. The periods reviewed in this section varied from 2000 to 2021, spanning between 9 to 19 years, making it more difficult to say if this overall decline is significant. Moreover, it is important to notice the spatial and temporal heterogeneity of snow in the Karakoram region, and from that acknowledge the possibility of uncertainties in the data set.

Reanalysis dataset holds the advantage of providing extended temporal coverage and global spatial reach. Recent studies with this dataset also usually perceive a slight overall decline in snow trends in the region. However, these studies were more focused in investigating how snow reanalysis datasets perform in the region, especially in comparison with in situ observations and satellite data. The authors concluded that snow reanalysis datasets, including ERA5 and ERA5-Land, tend to overestimate snow cover and snow depth, in relation to in situ and satellite observations. (Li et al., 2022; Orsolini et al., 2019; Yan et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2021). Despite the good temporal performance of ERA5 and ERA-Land, with a significant correlation in snow trends in the Tibetan Plateau region, the snow cover overestimation error was due to the overestimation of snowfall and underestimation of temperature inherent in these datasets. Given the significant impact of precipitation and temperature biases, the acquisition of more precise meteorological data is essential to increase the accuracy of reanalysis simulations. (Orsolini et al., 2019; Yan et al., 2024)

An approach other than MODIS product and ERA reanalysis data, is model simulation. Ménégos *et al.* 2013 utilizes the MAR (Modèle Atmosphérique Régional) model, a Regional Climate Model (RCM), to study precipitation and snow cover dynamics over the Himalayas during March 2000 to December 2003. The study accesses regional wind and precipitation patterns, also seasonal snow cover variations,

revealing continuous snowfall in western regions due to both summer monsoons and mid-latitude cyclones, while the central Himalayas showed a distinct dry season from October to March, leading to variable snow cover influenced by monsoon and rare winter snowfall. RCM underestimate snowfall in the eastern part of the Himalaya, being more accurate in central Himalaya and in western Nepal. Moreover, attention was given to the need to perform simulations over longer period to analyze in more detail the snowfall inter-annual variability over the Himalaya.

The key results of the papers considered for this literature review are summarized in Table 2. Ultimately, we can perceive that no dataset is perfect, especially in complex terrains like the Himalayas, where diverse climatic and geographical factors challenge data accuracy and model predictions, emphasising the importance of combining more than one dataset for more complete analysis.

Table 2 Key Findings of Literature Review

Study	Methodology & Focus	Key Findings
Banerjee et al., 2024	MODIS snow data (2003-2020), analysis of snow cover trends , temperature, and precipitation correlations	SCA decline (-0.23%/year), strong elevation, temperature and precipitation correlations. In the Ganges basin, SCA was related to human impact.
Desinayak et al., 2022	MODIS snow data (2000-2017), altitudinal snow cover area trends, linear trend analysis	Minimal annual SCA decline (-0.0024%/year), central and eastern HKH most affected, elevation correlated.
Gurung et al., 2017	MODIS snow data (2003-2012), snow cover area analysis, and climatic and topographic correlations.	SCA decline, in a inverse SCA-temperature correlation, higher variability below 6000 m altitude.
Thapa and Muhammad, 2020	MODIS snow data (2003-2018), analysis of snow cover area and snowline altitude.	Slight but not statistically significant decrease in SCA, with SLA rising 13 m per year.
S. Thapa et al., 2021	MODIS snow data (2002-2014), analysis of snow cover area, hydro-climatic variables correlation in the Upper Ganges River basin.	Annual SCA decline correlated with temperature, precipitation, and elevation
Dharpure et al., 2021	MODIS snow data (2000-2019), analysis of snow cover area trends, sensitivity analysis of temperature and radiation on SCA trends.	Significant regional variability SCA with maximum SCA in the Karakoram region, with na increasing trend. Strong SCA-temperature and SCA- albedo correlations.
Dixit et al., 2024	MODIS snow data (2003-2021), analysis of snow cover trends, ERA5 climatic variables correlation.	Minimal annual SCA decline. High sensitivity of snow cover to temperature changes, elevation and slope.
Li et al., 2022	Comparison of snow datasets (ERA5, ERA5L, Passive Microwave data and WRF downscaled simulation model) from 1981 to 2018.	All datasets represented spatial snow patterns but overestimated snow depth compared to in situ observations. WRF model exhibited lowest bias in snow depth accuracy, outperforming reanalysis datasets. Only ERA5 and ERA5L had a reduction in annual snow depth.
Orsolini et al. 2019	Comparison of snow reanalysis datasets (ERA5, ERA5-INTERIM, (JRA-55) and (MERRA-2) from 2009 to 2013.	Overestimation of snow depth and snow cover in most reanalyses, especially ERA5, due to excessive snowfall. MERRA-2 and JRA-55 performed best for snow depth
Zhang et al., 2021	Comparison of snow reanalysis datasets (JRA-55, MERRA-2, GLDAS2, ERA5, and ERA5L) from 1981 to 2018.	MERRA-2 exhibited highest correlation with in situ observations. Snow depth varied regionally.
Yan et al., 2021	Comparison of snow reanalysis datasets (HMASR, MERRA2, ERA5, ERA5L, JRA55, CFSR, CRAL, and GLDAS) from 2001 to 2017, and impact of snowfall and temperature in snow models.	CRAL, GLDAS, HMASR, and CFSR performed better spatially, while ERA5L, ERA5 and JRA55, demonstrated superior performance in SCF annual trends. ERA5, ERA5L, and JRA55 overestimate SCF due to biases in snowfall and temperature estimates, while MERRA2 underestimates it, leading to poor performance in spatial and trend representation
Ménegez et al., 2013	MAR model (Regional Climate Model) on precipitation and snow cover from 2000 to 2003.	The model showed an underestimation of snowfall, but successfully access regional patterns and seasonal snow cover variations, as well snowfall correlations with climatic events such as the monsoons.

Chapter 3

3.1 Study Area

The study area includes the Karakoram, Western Himalaya, and Kunlun Mountains, precisely latitudes 20°N to 40°N and longitudes 70°E to 100°E, covering approximately 6.4 million km², here there are three of the most socially and hydrologically significant rivers in the world the Indus, Ganges, and Brahmaputra River (Figure 4). This region, often referred to as the "Third Pole", contains the greatest amount of snow and ice of the planet outside the polar regions, and serves as a critical water source for Asia, providing freshwater directly or indirectly to about 1.5 billion people across eight countries – Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, China, India, Nepal, Myanmar and Pakistan. (Gurung et al., 2011, 2017; Shrestha et al., 2015)

Figure 4: Study Area limits and main basins

The Ganges basin is the most densely populated, while Indus and Brahmaputra basins have the most extensive upstream areas (Immerzeel et al., 2010). Snowmelt and glacial melt contribute to all three river basins, with the Indus having the highest dependency on it, on the other hand, the Ganges and Brahmaputra are more dependent on monsoonal rainfall, however, they benefit considerably from the seasonal snowfall during the dry season (Shrestha et al., 2015). Sub-basins such as the Hunza, Gilgit, and Shigar in the Karakoram are relevant for understanding snow cover dynamics, as their runoff is dominated by snow and glacial melt. Together, these basins regulate water supply for agriculture, hydropower, and domestic use in this part of Asia. (Hussain et al., 2019; Shrestha et al., 2015).

3.2 Data Acquisition

The data source for this research is the ERA5-Land, the access of this dataset is free on the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store page. The Copernicus climate change services (C3S) provide ERA5-Land dataset for the period from 1950 to five days before the current date.

The download of the dataset used in this work was done in September 2024, for “ERA5-Land monthly averaged data from 1950 to present” and includes Snow Cover and Snow Depth, from January 1950 to December 2023 in monthly resolution. The data covers the geographical region 40°N to 20°N and from 70°E to 100°E.

3.3 Data Preparation

The snow cover (%) and snow depth (m) were obtained in NetCDF format covering the area from 20°N to 40°N and 70°E to 100°E at a spatial resolution of 0.01°, with approximately 2.4% of missing data (N/A). The sea accounts for most of the not accounted data in this case, since ERA-Land is a land-only dataset, that means it is not accounting for sea. Reanalysis data is a gridded product, and grid points are points along the latitudes forming a structured grid that represents spatial patterns in the dataset. As the horizontal grid resolution is 9 km, each grid point encompasses an area of about 81 km².

Snow cover represents the fraction (%) of the grid-box occupied by snow. Snow depth represents the average of the snow thickness on the ground. Such a volume of data

required the use of RStudio software for its manipulation. RStudio is an integrated development environment (IDE) designed for the R programming language, an environment for statistical computing and graphics, specifically suitable for data visualisation. RStudio is an open source and a free platform. For this study, `ncdf4`, `dplyr`, `ggplot2` and `Kendall` RStudio libraries were utilized for efficient data manipulation, transformation, and visualization.

3.3.1 Spatial Distribution Analysis

The spatial distribution of snow cover and snow depth was analyzed on an annual, seasonal and monthly basis. The annual mean values were computed, from 1951 to 2023, by averaging the twelve months of data, from December of the previous year to November of the following, to be in accordance with the seasonal cycles, because of that 1950 was not considered, since we do not have access to December of the previous year. After that, the same was done for two different periods: 1991 to 2023, so we have 30-year analysis, and 2000 to 2023, in order to cover a similar period with MODIS satellite observations for possible future comparison.

For a focused seasonal analysis, the snow cover and snow depth data were averaged into four meteorological seasons: Winter (December, January, February), Spring (March, April, May), Summer (June, July August), and Autumn (September, October, November), from 1951 to 2023. Subsequently, average seasonal values were also calculated for the periods 1991-2023 and 2000 to 2023, and then plotted into “seasonal maps” to facilitate visualization of seasonal variability. Additionally, the averages examination allowed the visualization of the season with greater snow accumulation, as well as the season with less.

Monthly spatial distributions were first mapped to understand in more detail the dynamics of snow throughout the year. For that, the snow cover data for each month from January to December for the periods 1991-2020, and 2000 to 2023 was processed. Moreover, the monthly mean values were examined in more detail to identify the month with more and less snow in general, and specifically the ones accounting for grid points entirely or not occupied by snow. These monthly fluctuations in snow distribution can be especially useful for climatic impacts and hydrological investigations.

3.3.2 Temporal Evolution and Trends Analysis

This section aims to investigate trends of snow cover the given area. A trend in data analysis can be seen as a “direction” of the data, observed over a specified period. We are interested in understanding meanly two things: the trend of snow cover along the years of the dataset, how this trend is distributed along the area.

This way, slope and its significance are calculated to quantify the rate of change in snow parameters, and indicate if snow cover is increasing, decreasing or stable. Slope alone does not tell if an increase or decrease in snow is really being observed as a trend, especially for climate variables in complex terrains. In fact, the significance of the slope must be assessed using p-values, with a reference of $p < 0.05$ indicating statistically significant trends. The term p-value is an abbreviation for probability value, it represents the probability of obtaining test results at least as extreme as the result observed, assuming the null hypothesis is true. To obtain a p value, we must perform a liner regression or the Mann-Kendall test. The linear regression model assumes that data follows a linear relationship, while the Mann Kendall is a non-parametric test, without assuming linearity.

Initially, to have an overall temporal trend and understand how our variable behaved along the years, the annual average for individual years is computed, and from that a linear regression is performed using the Sen-Theil test. The area in this study is extremely extensive, so even the indication of snow cover decreasing or increasing can still not be representative for it as a whole. To solve that, we also performed the spatial trend in snow cover, based on the slope of each grid point values for the whole period of data, illustrating how the snow cover changes locally.

Chapter 4.

4.1 Results

4.1.1 Spatial Distribution

The spatial distribution of snow cover and snow depth analyzed from 1951 to 2023, in three different time windows coordinates, based on 60501 grid points, with 2.4% (1,451 points) of not accounted data (N/A), the sea, is presented below:

Annual Mean Distribution

From 1951 to 2023, the annual mean of snow cover distribution across the given region shows consistently high values, particularly in high-elevation regions. If the region is divided into areas with no snow cover and areas with at least 1% of snow cover, then 48.6% of the area can be considered snow free, while 49% is classified as snow-covered. Overall, in the following shorter periods lower values in mean snow cover are observed, within 1991-2023 and 2000 to 2023, the gridded points with “no snow” going to 48.9% and 49.2% respectively.

Based on the snow cover maps generated, similar patterns were possible to be inferred: the snow concentrates in the eastern part of the Himalayas, however, the peaks of snow covering near 90%, or more concentrating in the western region, specifically where the Karakoram Mountain range spans, approximately between 70°E and 80°E longitude and 35 to 40° latitude. Specifically, for the 1951–2023-time window, of the grid points analyzed, 0.80% have a snow cover of 90% or more. Conversely, areas with no snow cover correspond to the lower areas in altitude, and mainly below latitude 30° N, including most of India, especially the central part of the country.

Most of the grid points covered by snow fell within the 25–49% snow cover range. In the subsequent periods snow cover shows from this range a slight fluctuation, that can be observed in the plotted maps. From 13.6% in 1951–2023 to 13.1% in 1991-2023, and 13.2 % in 2000–2023. The most accentuate decline is observed in the snow cover range of 50-74%, from 11.3% of grid points to 11% and lastly 10.5% in the shorter period. Conversely, there was a slight increase in grid points completely covered by snow cover (100%), going from 0.34% of grid points to 0.35% in both following periods, and on grid points less covered by snow (1-9%), going from 11.8% to 12.3%) and 12.5%, . Besides the presented results, the snow cover maintains a similar pattern regarding geographical distribution in all intervals, with peaks concentrating in high

elevation.

Regarding snow depth annual means, the analyses from 1951 to 2023 show that the deepest snow is similarly concentrated in the higher elevations with a similar pattern to the one observed in snow cover. The highest value of mean snow depth is 10 meters, in 0.311% of the points. In the map this concentration can be observed by grid points colored purple (Figure 5), where approximately 1.5% of the total points represent around 1 m or more of snow depth, with 0.311% values equal to 10 m. Following the tendency of snow cover, this remained stable in the three time periods, contrary to all the other snow depth group ranges presented slimly decreases, being the most expressive one, ranging from 0.11 to 0.3 m, going from 4.28 % of grid points in 1951-2023 mean, to 4.14% grid points in 1991-2023, and 4.01% grid points in 2000-2023 mean.

The findings mentioned on Mean Snow Cover and Snow Depth can be visualized in the following maps, which illustrate the annual mean distributions across the region in the three different periods (Figure 5) and in the table below (Table 3), summarizing the values presented.

Table 3 Distribution of Snow Cover (%) and Snow Depth (m) Across Study Periods (1951–2023, 1991–2023, 2000–2023): % total grid points.

Category	1951-2023	1991-2023	2000-2023
Snow Cover			
No Snow	48.6%	48.9%	49.2%
1-9%	11.8%	12.3%	12.5%
10-24%	10%	10.4%	10.3%
25-49%	13.6%	13.1%	13.2%
50-74%	11.3%	11%	10.5%
75-99%	1.9%	1.7%	1.6%
Full (100%)	0.34%	0.35%	0.35%
Snow Depth (m)			
No Snow	41.4%	42.1%	42.2%
0.0001-0.001	15.4 %	15.4 %	15.8%
0.0011-0.01	20.3%	20.3%	20.3%
0.011-0.1	14.1%	13.6%	13.35%
0.11-0.3	4.28%	4.14%	4.01%

0.31-0.9	0.749%	0.605%	0.511%
0.91-5	0.643%	0.630%	0.63%
5.1 -9.9	0.560%	0.557%	0.557%
= 10 m	0.311%	0.311%	0.311%
(N/A)	1451 (2.4%)	2.4%	2.4%

Figure 5 Spatial Distribution of Snow Cover (%) and Snow Depth (m) Across Study Periods (1951–2023, 1991–2023, 2000–2023), latitudes 20°N to 40°N and longitudes 70°E to 100°E. On the left there are Mean Snow Cover Distribution maps for the 3 studied periods, with the scale ranging from 100-0% Snow Cover. On the right, Mean Snow Depth Distribution for the three studied (1951-2023, 1991-2023, 2000-2023) periods with values ranging from 0 to 10 m

Seasonal Mean Distribution

For the seasonal analysis, is it possible to infer a higher coverage and accumulation of snow in Winter, while Summer, shows minimal snow covers, for all three window periods. In Figure 6, we can observe this pattern for the 30-year period of 1991-2023.

Figure 6 Seasonal Mean Snow Cover Distribution (%), 1991-2023, latitudes 20°N to 40°N and longitudes 70°E to 100°E. Seasonally Snow Cover Distribution maps for the 1991-2023 studied periods, with the scale ranging from 100-0% Snow Cover: Winter, Spring, Summer and Snow.

The higher accumulation of snow in winter 1991-2023 can be inferred by the fact that the 10.9% of the grid points presents 90–100% snow cover, with 1.07% being totally covered by snow (100%), where elevations are highest. In spring, the melting season, 90–100% snow cover decreases to 8.2%. Summer and Autumn have the lowest values, with only 0.35% of grid points totally covered by snow. Autumn marks the beginning of snow accumulation, while summer has higher temperatures, the mean of 0.35% represents the average percentage of the region totally covered by snow all year, in all seasons, and are in accordance with the annual mean of fully covered grid points, which is also 0.35% in the Annual Distribution Analysis.

To have an idea of how much of the area is not covered by snow each season, the

percentage of grid points with snow cover lower than 1% coverage was calculated for each season. This value was highest in Summer (63.5%) however, the lowest value was not Winter (54,5%), but Autumn (45%) instead. That does not mean that Autumn has “more snow” than Winter, instead it tells us that Autumn has more grid points with at least 1% of snow cover than Winter does. Autumn is the accumulation season, forming the initial snow layer, and for that it requires snow to fall. If, for instance, snow falls and accumulates in lower areas, it is possible that the snow is not further retained in following seasons. Conversely, in higher elevations way more snow is observed in Winter than in Autumn, that probably related to lower temperatures.

Finally, regarding snow depth, the average intraseasonal change was not that expressive, as the percentage of grid points with snow depth exceeding 1 meter remained similar across all seasons. Table 4 presents the mean representative values of seasonal variations in snow cover and snow depth for the 1991-2023 period in the given area.

Table 4 Seasonal Snow Cover and Snow Depth Distribution, 1991-2023 period

Season	90-100 % Snow Cover	100% Snow Cover	Snow Depth > 1m	Snow Depth = 10 m	No Snow (0-0.9% Snow Cover)
Winter	10.9%	1.07%	1.48%	0.311%	54.5%
Spring	8.2%	1.63%	1.61%	0.311%	53.9%
Summer	0.6%	0.35 %	1.48%	0.312%	63.5%
Autumn	0.6%	0.35 %	1.46%	0.312%	45%

Monthly Mean Distribution

The highest snow cover values were observed in January, February and March, with above 12% of grid points exhibiting 90–100% snow cover. Starting from April, a significant decline in snow cover was observed, arriving in July and August being potentially the months with less snow, where around 67% of the representative grid points presented were less than 1%, covered by snow. This is in accordance with the fact that this month the temperatures are higher, leading to minimal snow retention.

If we compare the two data periods, 1991-2023 and 2000-2023, the standard is the

same, with more snow in winter months, and less in summer months. However, overall, more grid points with higher snow cover are observed in the longer period. For instance, the highest month in both periods, with 14.6% of the grid points above 90% covered by snow, while this value dropped to 14% in the 2000-2023 average.

The snow depth monthly analysis further supports the snow cover distribution. Following the seasonal tendency, values above 1 m tend to fluctuate less than lower values. In special, the snow depth at 10m remains stable throughout the year (~0.311–0.312%). However, the 0.1-0.3m snow depth shows strong seasonal variation, peaking in the winter months (January-March) and dropping in summer (July-August), consistent with rising temperatures.

Table 5 and Figure 7 illustrate the observed snow cover and snow depth changes throughout the months and between the two studied periods.

Table 5 Monthly Snow Cover and Snow Depth Distribution, 1991-2023 period & 2000-2023 period

1991 2023	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Mean Snow Cover (%)	27.1	27.3	25.3	22.2	16.8	9.29	3.46	2.55	5.27	12.8	18.5	22.2
90- 100% Snow Cover (%)	12.8	14.6	13.5	10.4	6.34	2.02	0.64	0.5	0.491	0.625	3.76	7.94
100% Snow Cover (%)	2.59	5.39	5.35	3.87	1.63	0.39	0.355	0.352	0.352	0.355	0.364	1.07
Snow Depth = 10 m (%)	0.311	0.311	0.311	0.312	0.312	0.312	0.312	0.312	0.312	0.312	0.312	0.312
Snow Depth 0.11- 0.3 m (%)	4.64	5.44	5.04	4.67	3.31	2.06	0.570	0.109	0.086	0.086	0.364	2.28

Mean Snow Depth (m)	0.107	0.117	0.126	0.129	0.122	0.105	0.0936	0.091	0.0913	0.0931	0.0967	0.101
No Snow (%)	43.7	47.5	51.1	53.7	55.6	59.9	67.6	67.0	59.8	54.8	50.2	44.6
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2000 2023	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Mean Snow Cover (%)	26.2	26.8	24.7	21.55	16.8	9.26	3.27	2.45	5.34	12.5	18.2	21.7
90-100% Snow Cover	12.3	14	12.8	9.7	6.14	1.9	0.61	0.5	0.5	0.614	3.33	7.67
100% Snow Cover	3.15	5.43	5.35	3.96	1.66	0.39	0.357	0.352	0.352	0.356	0.369	1.15
Snow Depth = 10 m (%)	0.311	0.311	0.311	0.311	0.312	0.312	0.312	0.312	0.312	0.312	0.312	0.312
Snow Depth 0.11-0.3 m (%)	4.43	5.28	4.88	4.26	3.38	2.10	0.476	0.107	0.0843	0.0876	0.403	2.21
Mean Snow Depth (m)	0.107	0.117	0.126	0.129	0.122	0.105	0.0936	0.091	0.0913	0.0931	0.0967	0.101
No Snow Cover	43.8	47.4	51.4	53.8	55.7	59.9	68.3	67.0	60	55	49.9	44.7

Figure 7 Monthly Mean Snow Cover Distribution maps, for the 2000-2023 study period , latitudes 20°N to 40°N and longitudes 70°E to 100°E, with the scale ranging from 100-0% Snow Cover. January, February, March, April, May, June, July, August, September, October, November and December.

4.1.2 Temporal Evolution and Trends

In the previous section we observed that the snow cover annual means are apparently getting lower in more recent years. Still, this alone is not enough to say that snow cover is decreasing or not. To have an overview of this evolution in time, linear regression of annual mean snow cover values from 1951 to 2023 was assessed. The

slope of -0.028 indicates a decrease in snow cover of 0.028% per year or 0.28% per decade. The negative trend is significant, with a p-value far below 0.05 (6.23e-6). In order further confirm that, Mann-Kendall test was conducted, this non-parametric test assesses the presence of a monotonic trend in the data without assuming normality. The test delivered a tau value of -0.361 with a p-value of 6.48e-6, confirming a downward trend in snow cover over time. The tau value, different from the slope, does not assess the magnitude of the change, just the direction, when it is positive the tendency is of increase, when it is negative, the tendency is of decrease.

Examining individual years, the year with the highest snow cover was 1957, with an average coverage of 19.9 %. In contrast, the year with the lowest snow cover was 2016, with 13.7% average coverage. The individual years mean plots, plus the slope values and statistical significance are summarized in the figure and table below (Figure 8 table 6).

Figure 8 Trend in Snow Cover Annual Mean along 1951-2023

Table 6 Statistical Trend and Significance of the Trend in Snow Cover Annual Mean 1951-2023

slope	-0.28%/per decade
p-value (Linear Regression)	6.23e-6
p-value (Mann Kendall Test)	6.48e-06

To assess whether the trend has intensified in recent decades, the analysis was repeated for two sub-periods: 1991–2023 and 2000–2023. The results show that the rate of decline has accelerated with a slope of -0.060 in the earlier period. This suggests that snow cover loss has indeed accelerated in most recent decades. However, in 2000-2023 the trend is no longer statistically significant, with a p-value > 0.05 (Table 7).

Table 7 Statistical Trend and Significance of the Trend in Snow Cover Annual Mean 1991 - 2023 and 2000-2023

	1991-2023	2000-2023
slope	-0.60%/per decade	-0.49%/per decade
p value	0.0016	0.11

Illustrating the regional spatial distribution of this negative trend in snow cover, the map below shows us that the reduction in snow ranging between 2% to -4% per decade (Figure 8). In the figure below, red represents the negative trend, while blue the positive trend, and white represents no annual trend or no snow. The predominancy of negative trend seems to be more pronounced in the eastern part of the area, ranging between longitudes 90-100°E, in relation to the rest of the area. In the east as well, we can see a higher positive yearly slope being more present. Overall, the mean slope was of -0.28/per decade, being in a proportion of 15.2% positive while 84.8% negative. (Table 8).

Figure 9 Annual Trend in Snow Cover, 1951-2023, latitudes 20°N to 40°N and longitudes 70°E to 100°E,

before the statistical significance test, with scale ranging red (negative slopes from -0.4%/year) to blue (positive slope until 0.2%/year)

Table 8 Mean Slope per decade 1951-2023, percentage of positive slope, percentage of negative slope

Mean Slope	-0.280%/per decade
% positive slope	15.2
% negative slope	84.8

It is called “apparent” trend, because each grid points slopes were not yet tested statistically. Even though overall, the 1951-2023 temporal evolution that been assessed previously in this section, with the linear regression that was further confirmed its significance from the p-value <0.05, showed indeed a decreasing trend, this can vary throughout the region, considering its sizes and especially the climatic particularities along the region, we cannot affirm just with that that the trend is negative for the whole region.

The Mann-Kendall test was performed, this time individually for each grid point slope. After that, the “not significant slope” was removed from the plot, resulting in the representative map below, with negative trends in red, positive trends in blue, almost stable trends (values close to zero) in white and “not significant” or no trend in gray. It was noted that 23% of the whole area accounted for a significant slope (Figure 10). Considering only significant slope values, we had 1.7 % with a significant positive trend, while 98.3% presented a negative trend, revealing instead a more accentuated negative slope, probably because of the loss in significant positive trends, if compared with the previous plot. See below the values mentioned (Table 9) and the representative map of the Trend in Snow Cover (Figure 11).

Figure 10 Annual Trend in Snow Cover, 1951-2023, latitudes 20°N to 40°N and longitudes 70°E to 100°E, after the statistical significance test, with scale ranging red (negative slopes from -0.4%/year) to blue (positive slope until 0.2%/year)

Table 9 Mean Slope per decade 1951-2023, percentage of positive slope, percentage of negative slope, after statistical test

Mean Significant Slope	-0.87% /per decade
% positive slope	1.7
% negative slope	98.3

4.2 Discussion

4.2.1 Representativeness of the Dataset & key findings in comparison with literature

This thesis aimed to bring an analysis of the spatial and temporal distribution of snow cover in the Himalayan region with reanalysis of ERA5-Land, from 1951 to 2023. In this chapter, we are going to discuss whether the reanalysis dataset was indeed representative, and as well the most interesting results and if those aligned with the literature review presented previously, in Chapter 2.

At first, the annual mean snow cover and depth calculations from the reanalysis

monthly dataset reflects the expected snow distribution, that usually correlates higher snow coverage where there is higher elevation. Moreover, it was possible to observe consistency between snow cover distribution and the respective snow depth distribution, with no apparent discrepancies or unrealistic representations. Additionally, when it comes of percentage of the area with snow, if we account the whole area, and consider “not covered by snow” any grid points below 1% snow cover value, we got a proportion of around 49% of grid points showing no snow, and 51% showing at least 1 to 100% of snow cover. However, it is important to point out that as Orsolini et al. 2019 stated, reanalysis datasets such as ERA5-Land may overestimate snowfall, leading to higher snow cover and snow depth values than those observed in situ.

When it comes to seasonal and monthly patterns, the analysis also was quite representative and apparently accurate, with Winter presenting highest snow cover, peaking in February, following with Spring, the melting season, showing special reduction in April for high snow cover grid points, then Summer with the least snow-covered gridded points, especially low in August, and Autumn, marking the restart of accumulation, with a higher area covered with at least some snow. In the literature, the MODIS based analysis also presents the peak of snow generally in February as well, with the minimum in August. Past studies usually show that accumulation starts in Autumn and continues through winter, which supports the observation that Autumn registers more grid points with some snow than Winter. Moreover, literature often attributes the maximum accumulation in February to maximum snowfall in this month (Dharpure et al., 2021).

Reanalysis datasets, including ERA5-Land, usually show regular seasonal cycles, with snow cover grows almost continuously during the cold season and peaking in February or March, like we observed in this research, however literature points out a difference in this regular pattern from in situ observations, showing at times rapidly fluctuating snow rises with little snow accumulation during the winter (Orsolini et al., 2019). Snow cover should not necessary present a regular pronounced seasonal cycle in the regions, since it depends on many variables, such as duration of the monsoon.

A particularly interesting finding from the analysis is the estimated decline in snow cover for the whole area of approximately -0.28% per decade. The recent decades show an even more accentuated loss, of roughly -0.60% per decade considering 1991–2023 window time. This is aligned with recent studies indicating also snow cover negative trends (Banerjee et al., 2024; Desinayak et al., 2022; Gurung et al., 2017;

Thapa et al., 2021). The 2000-2023 period, chosen specifically to be comparable with satellite products results, that start in 2000, did not show statistical significance in decline. Ideally, at least 30 years are needed to confidently detect a trend, so this lack of significance is not entirely unexpected.

Regional disparities in snow cover trends are expected in areas as the Himalayas, as observed by Dharpure et al. (2021), that noted declining trends in the Eastern Himalayas, while the Western and Central Himalayas showed at some points, more stable or slightly increasing trends. The region identified by Dharpure in the 2021 paper as "EH" (Eastern Himalayas), spanning roughly from 89° to 95° E longitude, and 25 to 30° N, exhibited a declining trend, although not significant, possibly due to the relatively short data period (2000-2019) of MODIS products. Similarly, the present work observed a more pronounced negative trend in the eastern part of the range, particularly between 90° and 100° E, with significant trends over longer study periods (1951-2023) but no significant trends in periods shorter than 30 years (2000-2023). In contrast, the Karakoram range, that spans approximately between 70°E and 80°E longitude, and 35° to 40° N latitude, in the referred work, presented the more considerable positive trend in snow, however, in our case, the Karakoram range showed likely mixed trends, with the positive one being non-significant (p value > 0.05). This suggests that while there may be a slight positive trend, it cannot be confidently attributed to a long-term or meaningful change.

Finally, as Ménegez in 2013 already pointed out the difficulty performing short analysis to access snow cover dynamics over the Himalayas, because of the likeability of changes in regional snow fall due to the differing climatic influences that the quite variable duration of the monsoon, and how it affects different the different areas of the region.

4.2.2 Study Limitations

While the dataset reliably captures snow spatial distribution, elevation dependency, and temporal trends, and benefits from large, gap-free coverage, it still has several limitations that should be addressed. The most significant reasons of biases is the overestimation over snow cover, are due to the overestimation of precipitation from ERA5Land. In addition, the seasonal cycles observed in ERA5Land are often considered "too regular" compared to real-world conditions. (Orsolini et al., 2019) This regularity might not fully reflect the natural variability present in snow

cover due to factors such as abrupt climatic shifts or irregular snowfall patterns.

Even being continuous data and gap free data, can still influenced by assumptions and approximations made during model simulations, which may not always match actual in situ conditions, implying the need to use ideally more than one dataset. Another limitation given to the fact that the area covered in this study is extremely heterogeneous and large, with local climate and topographic factors changing completely from one place to the other, it may also be necessary to perform a closer examination or even subdivide the region into smaller, more manageable sections to better capture regional variations and trends in snow cover dynamics.

4.3 Conclusion

In this study, ERA5 Land reanalysis dataset was used to examine the spatial and temporal distribution of snow cover and snow depth, inter and intra annually, along with snow cover trends in the Himalayan region from 1951 to 2023. Two other time periods were considered, 1991-2023 and 2000-2023, for similar aim, but also to observe differences between shorter to longer periods of data.

Overall, the results show a visible link between elevation and snow cover, higher altitudes tend to have more persistent snow and a deeper snowpack. 48.6% of the area has no snow cover, meaning that the grid point has less than 1%, while 49% is likely covered by snow. For snow depth, the most prominent areas of deep snow (close to 10 meters) align with the highly snow-covered regions (100% coverage), both representing around 0.3% of the area. Additionally, the results suggest that the eastern region has a larger area with snow cover, while the western area, particularly the Karakoram, shows a higher concentration of nearly 100% snow cover. The seasonal cycle is quite evident, with a strong peak in winter, especially in February, with higher snow cover and snow depth, and a marked drop during the summer months, particularly in August. Snow cover varies more than snow depth, the last one remains more stable across the seasons compared.

For trend, was observed decline in snow cover for the whole region, estimated to be at -0.28% per decade, with a more pronounced loss of -0.60% per decade during the 1991–2023 period, and a not statistically significant trend of -0.49% per decade for 2000-2023, likely due to the short duration of the dataset. The Karakoram and western

Himalayas show less pronounced changes in snow, with some areas even suggesting mixed trends, however some of them were not statistically significant. In the eastern part, the trend remained more statistically significant, further confirming a decline trend.

Given the enormous and heterogeneous study area, it might even be useful in future work to break it down into smaller regions to get a clearer picture of local trends or even combine the work with more climatic variables to better investigate the correlation of trend and climate conditions. Considering all mentioned, we can conclude that the study provides indeed valuable insights into how snow cover is distributed and evolving in the Himalayas, further confirming the representatives of the ERA5 Land for the variables utilized, this however, not without onloading the study limitations and future need to combine it with others reanalysis datasets and satellite product

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